

Being Black Skinned: A Doomed Fate? Brazilian Voices and the Others

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Abstract

The present endeavor is a textual analysis methodology study of Ralph Ellison's *Invisible Man*, Zora Neale Hurston's *Their Eyes Are Watching God*, Ahmadou Kourouna's *Waiting for The Vote of Wild Animals*, Aminata Sow Fall's *La Grève des Bàttu*, and Paolo Scott's *Phenotypes* to show that Blacks all over the world are not happy. They are not happy because of the Biblical curse in Genesis9, but because of the combination of the following three social factors that help keep them down: the poverty the world of the Blacks, Blacks frustrating Blacks and the humanity denied to Blacks by the corporate world in the West. These three ideas constitute the backbone of this study.

Keywords: blacks, poverty, exploitation, dehumanization, injustice, corporate world, and discrimination.

Introduction

In the days of slavery and colonization Blacks' distress was interpreted as a consequence of a Biblical curse: it was commonly believed that Blacks inherited their miseries on Earth because of Noah's curse in Genesis9. This interpretation of the appalling conditions of Blacks, especially in the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries, is now judged as racist. Nevertheless, such an interpretation well served Western imperialists' intentions in Europe and the Americas (in the heyday of the Atlantic Slave Trade) and in Africa and in the Americas (under European colonization) -Noah's decision that Canaan should be the slave of Shem was perceived as God's command that Black Africans should be the slaves to white Christians.

Today, the conditions of the great majority of Blacks have not improved much all over the world despite the end of slavery and the independence of the countries that previously were colonies.

In the U.S.A., for instance, the specter of the cold-blooded killing of George Perry Floyed in Minneapolis by a white police officer who strangled him to death by pressing his knees on his neck while the whole scene was filmed by a witness who could do nothing to help, on May25, 2020 is still vivace in people's mind. Still closer; the 29-year-old black Tyre Nichols died on January10, 2023; seven days after being brutally beaten by five black policemen in Tennessee while the scene was filmed by a standby who could not challenge the policemen.

In Brazil police brutality towards black Brasileiras is in increase today. CNN revealed that "um negro é morto pela polícia a cada quatro horas" (a black man is killed by the police every four hours)¹. Another Brazilian Source writes that "dados do Monitor da Violência mostram que em 2020 no Brasil 78% dos mortos pela polícia eram negros. O número refere-se às vítimas das polícias militar e civil e significa que quase quatro a cada cinco pessoas mortas pelas polícias em 2020 eram pretas ou pardas" (data from the Violence Monitor show that in 2020 in Brazil, 78 percents of those killed by the police were black. The number refers to victims of the military and civil police and means that almost four out of five people killed by the police in 2020 were black or brown).² In addition to police brutality the rate of poverty among Blacks continue to grow to unprecedented height. The favellas once multicolored (See Carolina Maria de Jesus's *Child of the Dark*) are now turning darker and darker.

In the book *América in Letters*, under the subtitle: Literary Interventions from Mexico to the Southern Cone Mamadou Badiane noted that

Black people in the Americas continue to protest prejudice and injustice, battling against marginalization and identity issues in their host communities. In the United States, a vast number of Black men, women, and children have been shot or brutalized by the police. While the culture of anti-Blackness in policing is pervasive, (Badiane,2022, p.220).

In Haiti, the elected president was recently killed, leaving the country almost in the hands of various gangs who are now ruling the country through terror and assassinations of all kinds. In West Africa civil wars follow on from each other. The war in Mali had hardly finished in 2013, as a result of assistance from the French army and navy, when another war started in Central Republic of Africa. Nigeria has been fighting for years against the Boko Haram Islamist insurgents. In Sub-Saharan Africa countries like Togo, Ivory Coast, Niger, Burkina faso, Republic of Benin...suffer recurrent deadly attacks by various Jihadist movements on the unarmed populations.

To what extent can the everyday lived effects of colonisation and slavery in the lives of Blacks be traced in literature from Africa and African Diaspora these twentieth and twenty-first centuries, and how this is reflected or contradicted by the historical accounts of the time? This is the concern of the present investigation which is based upon a textual analysis of Ralph Ellison's *Invisible Man*, Zora Neale Hurston's *Their Eyes Were Watching God*, Ahmadou Kourouma's *En attendant le vote des bêtes sauvages (Waiting for the Vote of the Wild Animals)*, Aminata Sow Fall's *La Grève des Bâttu (The Beggars' Strike)* and Paolo Scott's *Phenotypes*.

Many critics have addressed issues that have to do with the sad conditions of the Blacks in the world. But none of them put together Africans and the Blacks in Diaspora. The Book, *Amefrica in Letters*: Chapter Title: AFTERWORD. Racial Encounters in the Americas in Times of Black Lives Matter by Mamadou Badiane in *Amefrica in Letters* and David G. Hellwig's "Racial Paradise or Run-around? Afro-North American Views of Race Relations in Brazil" did a remarkable job in comparing the situations of the Blacks in Brazil and in the United States of America.

In order to present a convincing argument, the present investigation is divided into three parts: Poverty of the Worlds of Blacks; How Blacks Frustrate Blacks; and The Negation of Black Humanity by Corporate Interests in the West.

Right from the start, this endeavor rejects the view that Black peoples are suffering today as a result of Noah's curse and argue that the condition of dissatisfaction of Blacks today all over the world stems from the workings of three unscrupulous forces: Poverty, Post independent African Rulers, and Western Imperialism.

I. Poverty of the Worlds of Blacks

This first part of the work intends to show the general environment of poverty, miseries of all kinds in which the vast majority of Blacks reside all over the world. Literary works describing the poverty of Blacks abound. However, this paper limited itself to the five major texts cited above for two major reasons. First these texts can be said to constitute canons. Their readership is so wide. Despite the fact that they were old pieces of writing to the exception of *Phenotypes* they still retain the attention of Critics worldwide as my cited sources show it. The second reason for the choice of these texts comes from the need to link their contents with the socioeconomic conditions of Blacks from the aftermath of slavery to today. The paper agrees with the opinion that art for art's sake cannot be applied to writings by Blacks. They have always written to dramatize their socioeconomic conditions. The Harlem Renaissance Movement (1920s) and Negritude (1930s) which represented two major literary movements in the USA, Africa and the Caribbean developed as a way of righting wrong images of Blacks as spread by the imperialist West.

With the story of Trueblood in *Invisible Man*, the reader is thrown into the Blacks' world of poverty. Trueblood who impregnated his own daughter explains his act by the fact that the night was very cold, they did not have the means to warm the room. So, to keep from freezing his daughter had to cling to him on the mat. That was how he ended up sleeping with his own daughter. Under normal circumstances children are expected to have their own room. But here the Trueblood family could not afford this, which for them was a luxury. To this should be added the fact that they could not even keep warm in the winter. Conclusively Trueblood impregnated his own daughter because of poverty. According to himself, he regretted bitterly his action, that is why he was ready for his wife to kill him. When his wife raised the axe that was to cut his face into two, he did not do anything to protect himself or to dodge the blow. Another evidence that shows that he was sorry for his act was that he lamented that before his act he did not have any money. Now after his ignoble act money started coming his way. If he had had that money before he would not have done what he did.

Another evidence of the poverty of Blacks is that, once the invisible man lost his privilege to attend Dr. Bledsoe's Institution, his future to ideally become a famous black Scholar was shattered despite the fact that he had the talents needed for his ambition. He could not manage to get a job that would help him work through college like he was expecting to do after he was expelled from the College. He could not even let his parents know in the village because he would only add to their miseries when they knew he could not go to school. Let it be reminded here that the invisible man was just a boy and needed somebody to take care of him under normal circumstances.

Finally, it was because of the poverty of the world of Blacks that the invisible man got an opportunity to work to improve the lot of Blacks like he wished it. As a matter of fact the boy could not stand the eviction of the old couple in the middle of the winter because they could not pay rent. There was no indication from the text that they could have paid but did not. One could read in the novel:

"Don't tell me," She said. "It's all the white folks, not just one. They are all against us. Every stinking low-down one of them." "She's right!" a hoarse voice said. "She's right! They all is!" Something had been working fiercely inside me, and for a moment I had forgotten the rest of the crowd. Now I recognized a self-consciousness about them, as though they, we, were ashamed to witness the eviction, as though we were all unwilling intruders upon some shameful event; and thus we were careful not to touch or stare too hard at the effects that lined the curb; for we were witnesses of what we did not wish to see, though curious, fascinated, despite our shame, and through it all the old female, mind-plunging crying. I looked at the old people, feeling my eyes burn, my throat tightens (Ellison, 2022, p.292).

In *Their Eyes Were Watching God*, the conditions of the Blacks were not better. For Janie's Grandmother as soon as the former was of age to fall in love, she had to quickly put her into a safe hand. She had to find a good husband for her before white men took advantage of her as it was the case with her mother. Who was that safe hand? Logan Killicks. What qualified Killicks to be a safer abode for Janie according to her grandmother was that he was a successful farmer and as such could take care of her financially. However, Killicks seems not to be a good choice for the Beautiful Janie because he was old and seem more interested in making money through farming than take proper care of a younger and more beautiful wife. When Janie told her grandmother that she does not like Killicks and does not want to marry her, she confessed to Janie in these terms:

"'Tain't Logan Killicks Ah wants you to have, baby, it's protection. Ah ain't gittin' ole, honey. Ah'm done ole. One mornin' soon, now, de angel wid de sword is gointuh stop by here. De day and de hour is hid from me, but it won't be long. Ah ast de Lawd when you was uh infant in mah arms to let me stay here till you got grown. He done spared me to see de day. Mah daily prayer now is tuh let dese golden moments rolls on a few days longer till Ah see you safe in life." (Hurston, 2004, p.50).

Thomas F. Haddox in his paper "The Logic of Expenditure in *Their Eyes Were Watching God*" shares in the opinion that Nanny wanted Janie to marry Killicks for purely economic reasons though he reasoned that Janie was to become an instrument of exploitation in the hands of her husband Killicks. The critic went as far as citing those possessions that show Killicks was rich. Thus, Janie was to marry her husband simply because he owned the only organ in town among the black community, a house purchased and paid for, and sixty acres of land by the main road (Haddox 2001).

This same environment of generalized poverty is described in Ahmadou Kourouma's *En attendant le vote des bêtes sauvages*. Here we are no longer talking about Blacks in diaspora but Blacks in their own country. What happened is that in granting Independence to African countries the former colonists who were exploiting the Africans made sure they put in power African rulers who would be faithful to them rather than to the Africans. In most cases They put in power Africans who were not from kinship descent and thus susceptible to be challenged by the populations. So, these rulers resort to violence on the populations to stay in power. The Only threat to their power is the former colonist who put them into power. They know if they are not submissive to him, he can replace them with another more submissive person. This explains the multiplicity of government overthrows especially in Francophone Africa where France still continues exploiting its former colonies through these African corrupted leaders. An example of these corrupted African leaders is President Gnassingbe Eyadema of Togo who famished a population that was already poor, it is a known fact that Africa is the poorest continent in the world, because he wanted to celebrate the thirtieth anniversary of his seizure of power in the grandest way. Ahmadou Kourouma, who was not from Togo, could not remain silent on this act of heartlessness and lack of concern for the Togo population. He wrote:

For two full years, savings were put aside from the budgets of all holidays and all events. The funds reserved were credited to the thirtieth anniversary accounts that had been opened in the treasury and all the commercial banks in the country. Those accounts for the commemoration of the thirtieth anniversary of the assumption of power by the father-of-the-nation were, as numerous patriotic posters announced, referred to as the piggy banks of the entire nation and of the party. Public appeals had been made to businessmen, and public subscriptions were conducted in the schools, the post offices, the dispensaries, and at sports events. Schoolchildren had broken their piggy banks in order to send their savings to the father-of-the-nation so that he might have a fitting thirtieth anniversary. Prisoners had sacrificed meals for one day, officials, employees, and workers had given up a day's salary. All of these savings had been credited to the funds for the great feast of the thirtieth anniversary. Medals, pagnes, caps had been sold throughout the territory on all occasions. Private individuals had personally sent money orders to the president of the republic in order to participate in the collection of funds for the great feast of the century, the commemoration of thirtieth anniversary (Kourouma, 2001, pp. 223-224).

The writer further wrote that the big celebration was such a success that all economic activities in the country including farming, private undertakings, and government works were suspended for two weeks, that is until the end of the month when public servants were to be told "No Money to pay salaries" (Kourouma 2001). It is important to highlight here that all these donations and sacrifices by the population for the celebration were not for the most a manifestation of love from the part of the population for the dictator. But They were obliged to do it for fear of retaliation from the dictator because those who would not have participated would be taken for members of the opposition parties and dealt with by the dictatorial regime.

Poverty in the world of Blacks as far as *La Grève des Bâttu* is concerned is indicated by the situation of the beggars who were treated as if they were repulsive beings. In the beginning of the book they were referred to as "ces lépreux" (these leprous), "ces diminués physiques" (these handicapped persons), "ces loques" (these rags), "ombres d'hommes plutôt" (rather shades of men), "déchets humains" (human waste). The use of these negative adjectives to describe the beggars shows all the contempt that the rich have for the poor, here represented by the Beggars. Who refers to the beggars in these terms? The public servants who want to rid the town of dirt. Now these beggars were not constituted only with handicapped people, even if that is the case, it is morally wrong to call them what they suffer from. Besides, like the text will tell us later there are normal persons among the beggars. They resorted to begging to survive because they were finding it difficult to make the two ends meet. And since giving is one of the pillars of the Islam religion these beggars knew people would give them being in a country with majority Islam population. One could read in the book:

Tous rigolent lorsque Salla Niang, du seuil de sa chambre, assise sur une chaise, les deux mains dans un van posé sur ses genoux s'adresse à la foule impressionnante des *boroom bâttu* (les mendiants. Ils tendent, pour demander l'aumône, le *bâttu*, qui est une petitealebasse.) qui remplissent la cour de la maison, tout en comptant l'argent dans le van. Une multitude d'hommes et de femmes de tout âge; des grands et des petits, des infirmes et des valides, tirant tous leur pitance de la main tendue (Fall, 2001, p.24).

(All of them giggle when Salla Niang, from the threshold of her room, sited on her chair, with her hands in a van placed on her knees address the impressive crowd of *boroom battu* (the beggars. They held out to ask for alms, the *battu* which is a small calabash) who filled the courtyard of the house, while counting the money contained in the van. A multitude of men and women of all ages; old and young, infirm and able-bodied, who scrap their living from outheld hand).

If there were not poverty how to explain the fact that people who are in possession of all their senses would prefer to go and beg and stand the humiliation of being beaten on days of raids and still come back begging? Here is the story of Madiabel le Boiteux:

Il était forgeron dans son village natal. Un *baay jagal* (Réparateur). Mais les brèches des marmites à colmater et les queues de vieilles casseroles à improviser devenaient de plus en plus rares; les fourneaux ne se vendaient plus car l'intermédiaire qui venait les prendre pour les écouler à la Ville avait disparu un beau jour sans lui payer le produit d'un an de travail.

Pour nourrir et habiller ses deux épouses et ses huit bouts de bois, Madiabel décida à son tour à monter à la Ville. Il se convertit au *boroom bâttu* sans *bâttu*, mais main tendue. Les affaires allèrent mieux et il envoyait régulièrement à sa famille la ration alimentaire et les habits (Fall, 2001, pp.26-27).

(He was a blacksmith in his native village. A *baay jagal* (Repairer). But the gaps to fill in cooking pots and the stalks of old saucepans to improvise became rarer and rarer; the stoves were no more selling because the intermediary who used to take them to the city for sale disappeared a good day with the fruit of his one year's work.

In order to feed and clothe his two wives and eight end bits of wood [children], Madiabel decided in his turn to move to the city. Things got better for him, and he was able to send regularly food and clothing to his family.)

The critic John D. Ajala in his article titled "The Beggars' Strike Aminata Sow Fall as A Spokeswoman for the Underprivileged" demonstrates that Aminata Sow Fall in her book proves to be a true defender of the have nots (Ajala, 1990).

Finally, Paulo Scott's novel *Phrenotype* equally describes well poverty in the world of the Blacks. This is characterized in its major part by dire poverty in the midst of the richness of its white counterpart. A world where black Brazilians, mostly poor, were made to endure all evils from white Brazilians, without any complaint. Federico's former school mate declared in the bar Guitar Man: "You're never going to understand what it is to be black, to be a poor fucker getting hassled twenty-four seven on your street, in your neighborhood, in your city, you don't know," (Scott, 2022, p.121). The speaker here meant to tell Federico who is light skinned that he was unfit to understand the plight of the black Brazilian

and as such cannot be the defender of the race. As if to buttress this idea the critic Guillian Maris Jones noted in her paper, "Black Lives Abroad" that:

While government-sponsored racial quotas in universities and welfare programs like "Bolsa Família" seek to supplement the income of impoverished families and improve their access to education and public health, many Afro-Brazilians continue to live far below the poverty line. Possession of citizenship does not eliminate social inequalities, nor does it guarantee justice. The situation of Afro-Brazilians indicates that, despite the idealism of universality associated with citizenship, access to its various aspects is proportional to the quantity of melanin in one's skin and one's socioeconomic status (Jones, 2018, p.839).

Besides, the narrator right in the beginning of the book referred to Brazil as a land "where the practice of white men raping black and indigenous women had been allowed to run wild for centuries." It is crucial to notice that the writer highlights here how well spread the phenomenon and its extension in time. The indigenous women also share in the degrading fate. It can be concluded that the poor in Brazil can be dealt with in any way. The country's laws do not offer protection for them. This idea of the helplessness of the Blacks is further reinforced in the novel when a little black boy (the narrator's brother Lourenco) was humiliated among his peers by being called offensive names by his six-year-old white mates: Golliwog, Sambo, Magilla, Gorilla. It is acceptable for children who are fighting to exchange abuse (which should not be tolerated by parents). However, the scene as presented here does not show fight between the boys. The little black boy was abused simply because he disagreed with playing a game role during their break time. The book reads:

because in a game of tag during recess he hadn't submitted to their commands the way a Brazilian child who was considered black, according to the imaginary common law of those Brazilian children considered white in that year of nineteen seventy-three, was supposed to submit (Scott, 2022, p.11).

When the boys reported the matter to their mother, the latter had a strange attitude. She tried to minimize the incident, instead of taking the proper action of going to the children's school, reporting the matter to their teacher or director and demanding that the white boys be punished. Only one fact can account for such strange behavior of the boy's mother. She knows that it is their lot as black persons to be trampled on their rights by the white without any redress from the authorities (as cited in Gonzales, 1982), Eloisio Moulin de Souza wrote that:

In the Brazilian society, poverty and race are constructed together. She affirms that, in Brazilian history, the racial minorities were confined to the favelas, where the hygiene and health conditions are precarious and public polices are not there to protect, but to repress and frighten, benefiting the system with the maintenance of these conditions by the conservation of cheap workforce to be used (de Souza, 2019, p.12).

In view of all the above, one easily grasps Cesaire's frustrations about the "humiliated" and "unhappy" situation of Blacks worldwide (Badiane, 2022).

II. How Blacks Frustrate Blacks

This "humiliated" and "unhappy" situations of Blacks worldwide which frustrates Cesaire, the present endeavor asserts, is the consequence of the fact that Blacks are mean to each other, that is, the miseries meted out to Blacks come from other Blacks who are supposed to be guarantors of their happiness. As a matter of fact, Blacks do not agree among themselves to face together their common situation of various abuses. Rather some Blacks were used to frustrate their fellow Blacks most of the time by Whiteman. The paper refers here to the fact of Whiteman using Blacks to perpetrate wickedness on other Blacks because they do not want to be termed racists. Dr. Bledsoe is the typical example of such Blacks in *Invisible Man*. He was used by the white Trustees of the College to maintain Blacks in the position of sub servants of Whiteman.

He heartlessly ruined the career of the invisible man by sacking him from the college though he knew very well that the boy only obeyed to what the trustee asked him to do. He brought the Trustee to Trueblood's area because this is where the trustee asked him to drive him to. He later brought the trustee to the tavern When he felt bad because it was the only place where he could get help to assist the trustee who was about to faint and requested the boy to get him strong drink. Dr. Bledsoe knew all this. Nevertheless, he sacked the invisible man from the college, which stood as the only opportunity for the boy to be a success in life. His confessed reason for sacking the boy was that he was not clever enough to drive the trustee where he, the boy, wanted instead of obeying the Trustee. One could read in the novel:

white folk are always giving orders, it's a habit with them. Why didn't you make an excuse? Couldn't you say they had sickness -- smallpox -- or picked another cabin? Why that Trueblood shack? My God, boy! You're black and living in the South -- did you forget how to lie?"

"Lie, sir? Lie to him, lie to a trustee, sir? Me?"

He shook his head with a kind of anguish. "And me thinking I'd picked a boy with brain," he said. "Didn't you know you were endangering the school?"(Ellison,2022, p.152).

Let's assume that he sacked the invisible man from the college to protect the college. Did he need to ruin his future by sending him back to some of the trustees in New York (Where the boy intended to get a new start) to add to his troubles by asking the trustees not to give him any kind of assistance? The critic Yonka Krastei observed with insight that:

By contrast, in Ellison's work, black leaders like Bledsoe/Washington become accomplices in the white man's scheme and through their actions, which seemingly purport to bring "order" into black people's lives, they only help perpetuate and replicate these same structures of oppression (Krasteva, 1997, p.66).

Ras the Destroyer's decision to physically finish with the invisible man is equally understandable. He is more mature than the invisible man and he knew the invisible man to be used by the Brotherhood. Why has he not had enough patience to bring him to see clearly that the Brotherhood was just using him for the fulfillment of the objectives of the Brotherhood instead of the advancement of the Blacks. He too fell in the trap of the scheme of the Brotherhood which actually was maneuvering for the clash between Blacks and Whiteman. At the very point he attacked the invisible man, the latter has become aware of the true goals of the Brotherhood activities and would be willing to team with him and start over the struggle for the betterment of the lives of Blacks. The invisible man confessed towards the end of the novel:

I leaned against a stone wall along the park, thinking of Jack and Hambro and of the day's events and shook with rage. It was all a swindle, an obscene swindle! They had set themselves up to describe the world. What did they know of us, except that we numbered so many, worked on certain jobs, offered so many votes, and provided so many marchers for some protest parade of theirs! I leaned there, aching to humiliate them, to refute them (Ellison,2022, pp. 547-548).

Joe Starks in *Their Eyes Were Watching God*, unscrupulously takes advantage of the poverty of the Eatonville community to make a fortune for himself, although the Blacks there look at him as a Savior for the black race. When he first got there, it was easy for him to win their sympathy. He convinced them of the necessity for them to create an all-black town where they, including himself, will be free from the harassment of white. Since he has some money and was smartest among them, it was easy for him to become their leader. He then used his money to open the only shop in Eatonville where they could buy everything from groceries to alcoholic beverages. No wonder he became by far the richest man in Eatonville and could easily be elected Mayor of Eatonville, that is when he became a true tyrant for the people of Eatonville and started looking down upon the rest of the population. In summary, he became whiter than white for them. Discussing the Character of Joe Starks in his article: "The Hierarchy Itself": Hurston's *Their Eyes Were Watching God* and the Sacrifice of Narrative Authority, the critic Ryan Simmons asserted that:

These are characters who, despite questionable methods, use their immense (and seemingly innate) political talents to break open stagnant political situations and get things done that help people. Joe, for example, within days of his arrival in Eatonville, purchases additional land for the town, organizes the clearing of roads, builds a store and post office so that residents will no longer have to travel long distances for provisions, and installs a streetlamp (36-41). He is the sort of politician who makes civic prosperity and personal profit one and the same; as with Rataff and Willie Stark, it quickly becomes difficult to separate the well-being of the town from the interests of Joe Starks (Simmons, 2002, p.183).

This drunkenness of power made him end up ill-treating Janie. She was not his equal any more like things were when they first got to Eatonville. Janie became a wife who was to be all submissive to the powerful Mayor. His desires became orders for Janie who sometimes would rebel. She should henceforth stay behind the scenes, betraying what he promised her before she ran away with him from Logan Killicks'. He no longer fulfilled Janie's expectations of an ideal husband. Joe Starks has become a tyrant for both the Blacks of Eatonville and Janie and as such contribute to their everyday dissatisfaction. One could read in the novel:

Joe returned to the store full of pleasure and good humor, but he didn't want Janie to notice it because he saw that she was sullen and he resented that. She had no right to be, the way he thought things out. She wasn't even appreciative of his efforts, and she had plenty cause to be. Here he was just pouring honor all over her; building a highchair for her to sit in and overlook the world and she here pouting over it! Not that he wanted anybody else, but just too many women would be glad to be in her place. He ought to box her jaws!

But he didn't feel like fighting today, so he made an attack upon her position backhand (Hurston, 2004, pp. 73-74).

En attendant le vote des bêtes sauvages deals largely with how the post independent African leaders in Francophone Africa prove cruel to the populations who helped them come to power through various sacrifices and sometimes ruthless struggles against the colonizing countries. Everything happened as if they simply took the colonial masters' place. They

retained all the evils the colonial masters used to inflict on the populations: systematic torture and elimination of those who disagreed with them; unscrupulous exploitation of the populations, plundering of the mineral resources, the countries are among the richest in the world in mineral resources but the populations are the poorest in the world. Most importantly They become friends even the vassals of the colonial masters that these populations took all the pains to get rid of. The novel sadly records the following:

The stench—a mixture of death, infections, urine, excrement—was unbearable. A tremulous voice, the voice of a man at death's doorstep, came from the back of the cell.

“Kill me. For once in your life, be humane. Hang me. Shoot me. Kill me right now.”

“Shut your trap, filthy communist,” answered the fuming emperor [a post-independent head of state, the man with the hyena totem].

“For Christ's sake, kill me,” Koyaga! [Another post-independent head of state] “(now the voice was addressed to you). “Koyaga! You who are humane and a believer, pardon; ask him to finish me off. “...He had his own reasons. He did not even like to terminate the torments of common law-criminals by executing them. So why should he accord this favor to a political prisoner, a communist plotter, and a man from the Gbaya nation who had confessed. From the emperor's angry oaths, you gathered that Colonel Zaban was the prisoner chained to a Hook at the back of the cell. You knew Colonel Zaban quite well...According to custom, the emperor wanted the colonel to drink his own urine and eat his own excrement before he died. Zaban was the officer who...had engineered the success of the putsch and had made the man with the hyena totem head of state.” (Kourouma, 2001, pp. 145-146).

This is a sample of the way these post-independent Francophone African political leaders treat their political opponents when they are at all opponents. Sometimes they invented a plotted coup to get rid of the people they fear have enough influence to be chosen by the colonial countries' officials to replace them one day. In the present case it is the officer that helped the president seize power that this latter wanted to eliminate. Is it not ridiculous for an African to kill another African by accusing him to be a communist? The following quote from the article: Poverty in Freedom versus Opulence in Chains: Satirical Exposé of the Postcolonial Dictatorships in Kourouma's *Waiting for the Wild Beasts to Vote* by Isaac Ndlovo well corroborates this:

David Cauter in *The Spectator* of May 2003 describes the novel as ‘a witty and wholly authentic chronicle of black African atrocity.’ To use Abiola Irele's (2001) comment on an earlier novel by Ahmadou Kourouma, one can say this novel is “ nothing less than an epic of African adversity” orchestrated by the many dictators who have misruled the continent since it started to attain political Independence from European countries (as cited in Irele, 2001).[Ndlovo, 2012, p.60].

Two sequences in *La Grève des Bâttu*, show the inhumanity of the Blacks towards each other. The manner in which the beggars were treated. The novel referred to days of raffles when the beggars, mostly handicapped people used to be treated ruthlessly. It takes a heartless person to beat persons with handicaps such as the blind and the physically handicapped, who were made to run in all directions to avoid being lashed for the simple reason of coming to beg for their daily food at the spot where they are said to represent insalubrity in the city. This is the more incomprehensible because this happens in a Muslim environment where begging is one of the pillars of Islam. That is, a good Muslim should practice giving as much as he can. So, these beggars are there to help people fulfilling their obligation to give. How human beings can be said to represent insalubrity in the city is another thing that can be hardly admitted since the beggars in the novel were not said to wear gags. The book reads:

“ILS COMMENCENT à nous rendre l'existence impossible. Parce qu'on est des mendiants, ils croient qu'on n'est pas des hommes faits comme eux!”

C'est Nguirane Sarr qui parle. Il en a assez des tracasseries. Il a l'impression que ces “ fous-là” s'acharnent particulièrement contre lui...Pourquoi lui en veulent-ils? Lui qui se contente de rester à “son” feu, de ne jamais aller à l'assaut des voitures, sachant qu'il a affaire à des “patrons” qui n'aiment pas être dérangés et qui de toutes façons donneront la charité dans leur propre intérêt...

-Mais qu'est-ce qui leur prend maintenant? D'où leur vient cette rage?

-Ils sont mécahants, c'est tout.

Ils ne comprennent pas - qui leur dirait d'ailleurs?- qu'ils constituent une plaie qu'il est nécessaire de cacher (Fall, 2004, pp.43-44).

(``THEY START making it impossible for us to live. Because we are beggars, they believe we are not human beings like themselves! ``

This is Nguirane Sarr speaking. He is fed up with the hassles. Why are They holding grudge Against me? He is happy with sitting at ``his`` traffic lights, never to go to cars, knowing that he has to deal with ``bosses`` who do not like to be bothered and who anyway will give the alms in their own interest...

-But what is happening to them today? Where did their fury come from?

-They are wicked, that's all.)

The other instance of Blacks' inhumanity towards Blacks is provided by Dabo's uncle, who humiliates the boy in front of one of his friends. After the death of Dabo's father, he proved the only person in the family who was able to assist Dabo's mother financially. So, the bereaved woman and her children would regularly pay visits to the good uncle. Without any reason the uncle wrongly accused one of the orphaned children (Dabo) of having stolen things in his house on the occasion of one of such visits and in front of one of his friends who was with him. Since that day Dabo's mother stop visiting and was taking any money from that uncle and prefer going hungry with her children when there was nothing in the house and Dabo was enough old to witness this. That is why he had no patience for the beggars who do not have enough dignity to stop begging at their posts when they were said to represent insalubrity in the city. He would make it a personal challenge to drive the beggars out of the city when his superior in hierarchy entrusted him of the mission of ridden the town from the beggars, as to buttress this point, the critic Samba Gadjigo in his paper ``Social Vision in Aminata Sow Fall's Literary Work`` referred to the brutality of government officials, especially Keba Dabo and his Director Mour Ndiaye in an attempt to modernize life in the Senegalese Society (Gadjigo,1989).

Though *Phenotypes* by Paulo Scott did not discuss this idea in full details, the attitude of Federico's former school mate at the bar Guitar Man can be analyzed as an instance of clash among blacks. The young man without any evidence to prove it, treated Federico as a foe. In his words Federico is an opportunistic fellow. He wanted to get into the position of leader of black communities in order to make money. Now in the text, Federico is portrayed, despite his being a light skinned youth, as a character who looks at himself as being black and who is negatively affected whenever a black person is being victimized. He did not hesitate to urge his brother and friends to fight with the group of white boys and girls who called Roberta a bad name and would not apologize for what was said. He equally felt bad when the young Blacks at the army recruitment center were abused by one of the recruitment staff. Finally, he openly declared he was against the use of software to distinguish black Brazilians at a time when the government created a committee which includes Blacks with the intention that this committee would agree with the proposal of making use of such software, so that the government would declare it is the committee's decision. A committee where Blacks were represented.

From all understanding Federico's former schoolmate has no ground for making the statement that Federico is incompetent for leading in the fight for the betterment of the situation of Blacks. It does not look like being in the wrong when the conclusion is drawn that he was just jealous of the success of Federico. In fact Federico can be said to be a success because he is a university Graduate when his former school mate went into business and could not achieve any academic success. And this jealousy might be ruinous for the interest of the race. Let's suppose that Federico goes back to the bar and he killed him. This would be an ending of what Federico could do for the improvement of the conditions of Blacks in Brazil.

III. The Negation of Black Humanity by Corporate Interests in the West.

The paper here highlights the fact that Western interests all over the world seems not to recognize Blacks as human beings, for the most they are considered as subhuman. This explains why Blacks were used as beasts of burden during the period of slavery and later during colonization in Africa, the natural resources were plundered, and the continent was shared among the European nations as if the Africans do not exist at all. Today Europeans (especially the French) when giving independence to African countries made sure they put in power African leaders who proved to be their stooges in order to continue mining their resources without any return for the Africans.

The simple fact of the invisibility of the invisible man in *Invisible Man* bears witness to the fact that Corporate Interests do not acknowledge the humanity of Blacks. More specifically the first chapter of the novel illustrates well this point. The invisible man who proves to be a very bright student was invited to present a paper, which was rated outstanding by his school to the high officials of the school. But before his presentation a game was staged to entertain the audience. During this game a number of black boys were to be blindfolded and asked to fight each other until it remains only one winner. The invisible man was asked to join this group of black boys. This actually means that there is no difference between this bright black boy and the Other black boys. They are all the same in the eyes of school authorities. They were there to entertain like any object of entertainment. One could read in the novel:

All of the town's big shots were there in their tuxedos, wolfing down the buffet foods, drinking beer and whiskey and smoking black cigars. It was a large room with a high ceiling. Chairs were arranged in neat rows

around three sides of a portable boxing ring. The fourth side was clear, revealing a gleaming space of polished floor. I had some misgivings over the battle royal, by the way. Not from a distaste for fighting, but because I didn't care too much for the other fellows who were to take part. They were tough guys who seemed to have no grandfather's curse worrying their minds. No one could make mistakes in their toughness. And besides, I suspected that fighting a battle royal might detract from the dignity of my speech. In those pre-invisible days, I visualized myself as a potential Booker T. Washington. But the other fellows didn't care too much for me either, or there were nine of them. I felt superior to them in my way, and I didn't like the manner in which we were all crowded together into the servants' elevator (Ellison, 2022, p.21).

The same attitude of lack of recognition for an individual black person was shown by the college trustee Mr. Norton. Instead of bearing responsibility for his deeds. He preferred keeping quiet and allowed the invisible man to be sacked from the college. He did not look at him as a human being who has feelings and a dream to fulfill. Otherwise, he would have taken the defense of the boy by merely admitting that he was the one who asked the boy to drive him to the Trueblood cottage.

In a discussion of *Invisible Man* Cecil E. Bohanon posited with insight that:

Modern-day readers find it disconcerting if not shocking to think an intelligent young black man would be subject to the indignities of the Battle Royale or that such indignities would be accepted by a black person. Of course, as a novelist, Ellison was free to create an exaggerated and surreal scene to illustrate the reality of the social system of the pre-civil rights South, which has been well documented. In the mid-1940s, Gunnar Myrdal described the Jim Crow South as a society where racial relationships were strictly defined and enforced, where "all of these thousand and one precepts, etiquettes, taboos, and disabilities inflicted upon on the Negro have a common purpose: to express the subordinate status of the Negro and the exalted position of the white" (cited in Myrdal, 1944, p.66) [Bohanon and Vachris, 2020, p.442].

In *Their Eyes Were Watching God*, the story of the father of Janie is an illustration of the negation of Blacks' humanity by Corporate America. Here is a man, a schoolteacher, who sequestered a little girl for a whole night and raped her. His chastisement for committing such a horrible crime was just to drive out of the city, The novel did not make mention of any judgement in any court, which simply means that it might be a community decision. If the victim were a white girl, things would have been different. There would be prison sentences, and the story might be top news for journals. Here in the case of Janie's mother, the culprit was just asked to leave the city preventing the raped mother to even see again the father of her daughter, this punishment for such a crime might be interpreted as an attempt to close down the case. The rapist is not around, little by little the story might die out and be forgotten. That is how Janie ended up not having a father and so became the daughter of a runaway father, a child with a shame right from her birth. The book reads:

They'd push me 'way from de ring plays and make out they couldn't play wid nobody dat lived on premises. Den, they'd tell me not to be takin' on over mah looks 'cause they mama told 'em 'bout de hound dawgs huntin' mah papa all night long. 'Bout Mr. Washburn and de sheriff puttin' de bloodhounds on de trail tuh ketch mah papa for whut he done tuh mah mama. Dey didn't tell about how he wuz seen tryin' tuh git in touch wid mah mama later on so he could marry her. Naw, dey didn't talk dat part of it atall. Dey made it sound real bad so as tuh crumple mah feathers. None of 'em didn't even remember whut his name wuz, but dey all knowed de bloodhound part by heart. Nanny didn't love tuh see me wid mah head hung down, so she figgered it would be mo' better fuh me if us had uh house. She got de land and everything and then Mis' Washburn helped out uh whole heap wid things." (Hurston, 2004, p. 44).

Western imperialism in Africa did not end with colonization in Africa, as a general and particularly in Francophone African countries secret agreements were signed between France and the independent countries which allowed France to continue exploiting these countries. In order for these agreements to be fulfilled France has always managed to put in power in these countries African leaders, usually their stooges. These latter knowing that their being in power depends more on France than on the will of their populations turned to accomplices of Western imperialism and together they systematically continue to plunder the continent. Isaac Ndlovo posited with insight that:

Kourouma's novel derives its power from showing that 'what is' in Africa is that African leaders have taken political control from their erstwhile colonizers, but 'what might be,' that is freedom from poverty, economic underdevelopment and the people's genuine democratic rights to hold their leaders accountable, remain a receding point for the majority of the continent's citizens (Ndlovo, 2012, p.62).

Everything happened as if the resources' of the continent do not belong to the Africans. Former President of Central African Republic, Emperor Jean Bedel Bokassa, declared in an interview on television that President Giscard of France and France had mined the diamond of the country for years without any return to the country. This is what is termed today neocolonialism and more recently Francafrigue.

In *La Grève des Bâttu*, all the miseries inflicted on the beggars: lashes on days of raffles, frequent injunctions not to stay where they used to stay...that result in making the lives of the beggars more difficult coupled with the new complications for the givers of alms to observe a daily ritual is justified by the need to modernize. That is the need for the city to look like a Western city. Here, just like in the above paragraph, no consideration was given to the humanity of the beggars even to the givers of alms. Otherwise, the government would seek their consent before taking any action. Mour Ndiaye who was given charge by the government to rid the town of the beggars had had all the difficulties of the world to perform the sacrifice that was to make him Vice-President. If they had done things in collaboration of the beggars, these latter would have helped him perform his sacrifice. The critic Samba Gadjigo rightly commented that:

No doubt Fall's work has given a voice to millions of voiceless women in her society. Put together, her four novels also create a literary universe that goes beyond the already-classic theme of women's emancipation to explore the human predicament in a contemporary Senegalese society undergoing tremendous mutations. In each of her four novels the issue of social change is portrayed through the collective and individual drama of her characters. More specifically, Fall narrates social, cultural, and political behavior to illustrate the negative impact of unbalanced social change (Gadjigo, 1989, p.411).

Actually, the French colonial policy of assimilation believed that Africans should become 'white' to attain their humanity. African practices had to be banished because they become devilish practices. This idea still continues to affect the daily life of the Africans today, especially in the former French colonies. When Mour Ndiaye became a prominent political leader who was considered for the position of Vice-president of the country by the President, he needed a befitting wife. He had to marry his mistress who could speak French. His wife, who used to go to the marabout on various errands for her husband to become what he is, has to be pushed backward. The novel records that:

Mour a attendu ce moment précis où tous les rêves lui sont permis--''Monsieur le vice-président de la République et Madame''-- pour lui faire comprendre que son bonheur peut exister ailleurs qu'en elle; une fraîche jeune fille de dix-sept ans, secrétaire dans une agence de tourisme...Il avait été séduit par sa spontanéité, par sa jeunesse et surtout par l'aisance avec laquelle elle s'exprimait dans la langue officielle, ou lui-même, Mour, avait quelques difficultés (Fall, 2004, pp. 62-63).

(Mour has waited for this very time when he can entertain all kinds of dreams--'' Mister Vice-president of the republic and Madam'' to her [his wife Lolli] understand that his happiness can exist elsewhere than with her; a seventeen years old fresh young girl, secretary in an agency of tourism...He had been seduced by her spontaneity, her youth and mostly by the ease with which she expressed herself in the official language, with which, he himself, Mour, had some difficulties).

The last evidence of this analysis concerning the denial of humanity of Blacks by corporate interests, which contributes to the miseries of Blacks all over the world as far as Paolo Scott's Phenotypes is concerned is the dehumanization of black Brazilians by corporate Brazil which backs the government. The critics Melanie A. Medeiros and Tiffany Henriksen posited with insight that:

Persistent race and class hierarchies in Brazil are the result of and contribute to the discrimination and marginalization of working-class black Brazilians, including occupational discrimination (Alves 2010; Azevedo, 1959; Guimaraes, 2002, 2005; Hasenbalg, 1979; Santos & Inocencio, 2006; Silva, 1988, 2000). Black people in Brazil suffer from social and structural inequality—including unequal access to social resources such as health care, quality education, and adequate housing and sanitation—related to poverty and the lack of government investment in their communities (Silva & Hasenbalg 1992; Paixao, 2013; Sheriff, 2001; Telles, 2004; Twine, 1998 [Medeiros & Henriksen 2022]).

Federico in the beginning of the novel was seen as a member of a committee set up by the government to explore the possibility of using a software which will be used to distinguish Blacks from the rest of the Brazilian population. The implication of this new proposal is that the software will replace men and women who before had the charge to decide on the veracity of people's own declarations. How can a machine be able to perceive the complexities of race determination where human beings who are more competent are failing. Which software is able to show that Federico (who is very light skinned) and his brother Lourenco (Who is black skinned) are both Blacks? It appears evident here that the motive for the use of software to distinguish races might be somewhere else. This idea is further reinforced by the idea of the government to use one of its members who chairs the committee (that includes members of both races) to maneuver to make it to adopt the proposal of using software to distinguish races. The book reads:

A large portion of white society doesn't want to see black people up on their feet, They want the blacks to remain subjugated, enslaved, For a large portion of whites the presence of a black person in certain places shatters the sacred harmony of the environment, This to me is the point, it's what made me want to be a part of this commission, began Mauro, And I'm really sorry, but I'm going to keep going back over the subject of the software, We have to ask ourselves how much the news that this commission of ours is going to spend hours

arguing about the production of a piece of software for selecting black and indigenous quota students is just going to provide arguments for the racists, just as Federico rightly pointed out, he said (Scott, 2022,p.49).

Throughout this work, the point is made that the Blacks wherever they are found in the world do not feel fulfilled. Be it in Africa, or in the United States or in Brazil the Blacks are not satisfied with their socioeconomic conditions. There is no denying that art for art's sake in literature cannot be applied to writing by Blacks. Two of the major literary movements in the history of Blacks: The Harlem Renaissance Movements (1920s in the United States) and Negritude (1930s in Africa and the Carribean) proved to be works of Black militancy.

For this argument, Blacks in the world do not feel fulfilled because their ancestors were cursed as some interpretations of the Bible want to have it. They are not satisfied because of the combination of the following three factors as shown in the text. First, the poverty of the worlds of the Blacks. Wherever there are Blacks they are counted among the poorest. In Africa many Africans died at sea in a desperate to reach the shores of Europe considered by them to be na Eldorado. In Brazil and in America Blacks are killed every day by the hands of the police mostly by accident who take them for criminals because of their poverty. The second motive of dissatisfaction of the Blacks is the fact that, some of the Blacks who the other Blacks trusted unscrupulously betrayed them. This is mostly the case of the political leaders in Africa who Join hands with the Imperialist West to frustrate their own populations. At these should be added the few successful and ambitious Blacks who were used by the West to exploit the vast majority of the Other Blacks. Finally, the Corporate West do not look at the Blacks as individuals capable of mining and managing the immense natural resources of Africa and so make use of any means to take control f these resources. These same Corporate because of their prejudices work to perpetrate racism which maintain the Blacks in subservient positions all over the world. Eloisio Moulin de Souza reminds us that: ``Therefore, race was also built by capitalist forms of production. Many races were considered as animals, therefore not human, to justify their enslavement and use in the development of capitalism (cited in Ferguson, 2003) ``[de Souza, 2019, p.9].

For all these reasons the paper suggests that Blacks all over the world should understand that to blame everything about their present condition of dissatisfaction on colonization, slavery, and the white world does not give the whole picture. Blacks as well as white people should be held responsible. That is why the position of this paper is that to better the conditions of Blacks all over the world today, Blacks need to join hands with whites. The Underground Railroad was successful during the slavery period in the U.S.A. because it involved a close collaboration between black and white Americans. Finally, the paper is of the opinion that one of the solutions to stopping the spread of extremist Islam, especially in French-speaking Africa, is to improve the condition of the general population who feels that the world is unjustly skewed against them. They live in dire poverty while their leaders live in extravagant opulence.

NOTES

I have used English translations where available. Where I provide both the French and the English, the translations are my own.

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